

PHOTOCATALYTIC AND OPTIMIZATION OF HYDROGEN PRODUCTION USING SYNTHESISED BISMUTH FERRITE (BiBaKFeO₃) NANO PEROVSKITE

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Abstract: *Hydrogen is a clean renewable and sustainable alternative fuel. However, developing environmentally friendly and cost-effective means of hydrogen production is a global priority. Photocatalytic water splitting harnesses solar energy to produce hydrogen directly from water proffers. Photocatalyst BiBaKFeO₃ was synthesized by sol-gel method and calcined at 850oc for 3h, the BiBaKFeO₃ was characterized using X-ray flouresence (XRF) for elemental analysis, X-ray diffraction (XRD) for phase analysis, FTIR and TEM for bond types and morphology respectively. The optimum amounts of the Photocatalytic BiBaKFeO₃, Methanol as a sacrificial donor, Ni as a co-catalyst and pH were investigated for highest hydrogen generation by varying the quantities. 245Mmol-1h-1g-1of hydrogen was yielded with 0.75g of BiBaKFeO₃, 15% concentration of Methanol yielded 290Mmol-1h-1g-1of hydrogen, 1% of Ni solution as a co-catalyst yielded 290 Mmol-1h-1g-1of hydrogen, while at a pH of 4, 270 Mmol-1h-1g-1of hydrogen was yielded.*

Introduction

Hydrogen is an alternative energy source for the conventional fuel, which can fulfill the energy requirements in future. Hydrogen has also been used for industrial applications like manufacturing chemicals and several other industrial processes. The issues like limitations of the reserves of the fossil fuel and their environmental impacts are the main drivers for the hydrogen based energy (Ni et al., 2017). Hydrogen production from water through

photocatalysis is among the most environment friendly and potential options. Water splits into H₂ and 1/2O₂, and the dissociation of water occurs at 1.23 eV, which otherwise requires a very high temperature. To overcome these problems the photocatalytic way of hydrogen production through water splitting can be an alternative and cleaner route (Fan et al., 2009) Titanium dioxide was the first material used for electrochemical water splitting reaction by (Fujishima and Honda in 1972) under ultra-

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violet radiations. Following this, extensive attempts were made by different researchers all over the world to synthesize photocatalysts, most of which were effective in the UV while some being visible light active. Solar spectrum comprises predominantly of visible radiations ($\lambda = 400 - 700$ nm), so extensive attempts were subsequently made to design visible light active photocatalysts (Li et al, 2010).

Various photocatalysts like mixed oxides and perovskites, etc have been widely developed and studied for the photocatalytic hydrogen generation reaction (Liua et al, 2008; Kudo, 2006; Kanadeet al, 2008).

Perovskite are stable, crystalline materials with ABO_3 type structure, and shows flexibility in their composition based on large size rare earth or alkaline earth metals at A-site, while transition metals at B-site; a titanium oxide mineral made of calcium titanate (chemical formula $CaTiO_3$). The term is also used to refer to a class of compounds that share the same crystal structure as $CaTiO_3$, known as the perovskite structure. In 1839, Gustav Rose discovered the mineral in the Russian Ural Mountains, and it was named after the Russian mineralogist Lev Perovski (1792-1856). A variety of cations can be embedded in this structure, enabling the creation of a wide range of engineered materials (Yu et al., 2017). The potential environmental uses of perovskite-type catalysis materials, such as wastewater treatment, air purification, and the elimination of various organic contaminants, have drawn a lot of attention. The development of

nanoperovskite-based photocatalysts for efficient hydrogen generation through water splitting is Leveraging the unique properties of perovskite nanomaterials can significantly advance sustainable hydrogen production, aiding the global shift toward clean energy. Advantage of perovskite type structure is due to their valency and vacancy control, which enhances their catalytic activity (Kanade et al, 2008). These perovskite photocatalysts have shown to reduce the band gap energy and improve charge separation between photo-generated holes and electrons (Tanaka, & Misono, 2001). ABO_3 type Perovskite materials like $SrTiO_3$ (Liua et al, 2008) and $NaTaO_3$ (Kudo, 2006) etc. and also layered perovskite materials (Kudo & Miseki) show good photocatalytic activity for water splitting. There are many evidences for the photocatalytic activity of ferrite type perovskite materials like $LaFeO_3$ (Li, et al, 2010; Yang et al, 2009; Li, et al, 2007), $YFeO_3$ (Lu, et al, 2007), and $ReFeO_3$ (Niu, et al, 2005) etc. This has been systematically studied for photocatalytic hydrogen generation, by (Xia, et al, 2006) in UV light while very recently Parida et.al, reported the generation of hydrogen in visible light region (Parida et al,). Literature also suggests photocatalytic property of this material towards dye degradation reactions (Li, et al, 2010; Yang et al, 2009; Li, et al, 2007). This material therefore, deserves more detailed investigations towards its photocatalytic properties. The conventional synthesis of $LaFeO_3$ perovskite photocatalyst by solid state reaction with its

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large particle size has certain limitations including that of a low surface area. As an alternative method, in a study, the LaFeO₃ perovskite has been synthesized by sol-gel route, under ultrasonic treatment (Lishan, et al, 2007), with a view to improve the physical properties of this material. This project will synthesize (BiBaKFeO₃)nanoperovskites for photocatalytic water splitting providing a new pathway toward efficient, low-cost green hydrogen.

Materials and Method

A.R. grade Distilled water, Barium nitrate (Ba(NO₃)₂), Anhydrous Iron nitrate (Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O), Anhydrous Bismuth nitrate (Bi(NO₃)₃·5H₂O), Potassium nitrate (KNO₃), Citric acid (C₆H₈O₇·H₂O) with 52% purity, 1.54g/cm³ density and 1.23g/ml specific gravity, Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate SDS (NaC₁₂H₂₅SO₄), Hydrogen chloride (HCl) with 35% purity, 1.18g/cm³ density and 1.16 g/ml specific gravity, Sodium hydroxide (NaOH), Ammonium hydroxide (NH₄OH), Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), Ethylene glycol (CH₂OH)₂, Nitric acid (HNO₃) with 68% purity, 1.50 g/cm³ density and 1.51 g/ml specific gravity, Hexane (C₆H₁₄), Sodium thiosulphate (Na₂S₂O₃), Potassium dichromate (K₂Cr₂O₇), Sulphuric acid(H₂SO₄) with 98% purity, 1.88g/cm³ density and 1.8 g/ml specific gravity, Ammonia (NH₃), these chemicals were procured from Kaduna, Nigeria and were used for this research without further purification.

Synthesis

Doped Bismuth ferrite nanoperovskite (BiBaKFeO₃) was synthesized using Sol gel method Citric acid pathway. In a 250ml beaker 10.09 g citric acid was dissolved in 100 ml distilled water. It was heated to 90°C under stirring. 10ml of ethylene glycol was slowly added until homogeneous. 12.64g Bi(NO₃)₃·5H₂O, 12.93 g Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, 7.53 g Ba(NO₃)₂ and 0.32 g KNO₃ were added sequentially with continuous stirring until a slightly viscous solution was formed and the pH was adjusted with NH₄OH until the pH was 7. After an hour a dark yellow solution was formed and was dried in an oven to form a gel. Then the gel was 850°C for 3 h in a muffle furnace to form perovskite-type crystals.

Characterization

FTIR spectrometer was used to determine the functional group of all powders. X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) spectroscopy detected the elements present in the sample and their concentrations. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) was used to determine the morphology while X-ray Diffraction (XRD) analyzed and identified the phases in the synthesized BiKBaFeO₃ nano-perovskite,

Hydrogen Production

The photocatalytic experiment of water splitting was carried out in a photocatalytic reactor. The borosilicate glass reactor was enclosed in a galvanized iron (GI) rectangular box equipped with light source, stirrer, condenser and a gas collector. Upper wall of this GI reactor was kept movable for the reactor operations. The glass reactor of capacity 40 ml, with water condenser

was used for the photocatalytic water splitting reaction. The gas collector of 15 ml capacity was attached at the end of the condenser for the collection of gaseous product. A vacuum pump was used to evacuate the whole system. 20 ml of DI water was boiled to remove dissolved oxygen. It was then cooled and as catalyst BiKBaFeO₃ was added followed by addition of ethanol, and co-catalyst Nickel. The reactor was then fixed with the condenser, which was further attached with a gas collector. The whole experimental set-up was evacuated by using vacuum pump. The solution was continuously stirred using magnetic stirrer for uniform dispersion of the BiKBaFeO₃. The glass reactor was illuminated with two 200 W tungsten light sources for 4 h. After the completion of reaction, the gas collector was removed from the set-up and then evaluated on the GC equipped with molecular sieve 5A column using thermal conductivity detector (TCD).

Results and discussion

Characterization of BiKBaFeO₃

The XRF elemental analysis of the synthesis BiKBaFeO₃ given in Table 1 shows all the elements in their oxides. While XRD pattern of BiKBaFeO₃ is shown in Fig. 1, which shows well indexed diffraction peaks, clearly indicating the formation of orthorhombic ABO₃ type structure

(JCPDS card No. 88-0641). The synthesized BiKBaFeO₃ crystallizes in orthorhombic structure with the higher intensity peak at 2θ value of 32.16, which corresponds to BiKBaFeO₃(h k l) 002 as per the JCPDS card No. 88-0641. The FTIR spectrum in figure 2 shows strong absorption bands around Peak at 450cm⁻¹ and 560cm⁻¹, which corresponds to Bi - O and Fe - O stretching vibration bonds formation respectively confirming the formation of the perovskite phase. The slight shift in the absorption bands indicates lattice distortion due to successful incorporation of dopant ions into the BiFeO₃ structure. The TEM morphology of BiKBaFeO₃ formed indicating the nano-scale of crystals formed. Tables' 2-5 presents the amounts of the Photocatalytic BiBaKFeO₃, Methanol as a sacrificial donor, Ni as a co-catalyst and pH investigated for highest hydrogen generation by varying the quantities and keeping other parameters constant one after the other. 245Mmol⁻¹h⁻¹g⁻¹of hydrogen was yielded with 0.75g of BiBaKFeO₃, 15% concentration of Methanol yielded 290Mmol⁻¹h⁻¹g⁻¹of hydrogen, 1% of Ni solution as a co-catalyst yielded 290 Mmol⁻¹h⁻¹g⁻¹of hydrogen, while at a pH of 4, 270Mmol⁻¹h⁻¹g⁻¹of hydrogen was yielded.

Table 1: XRF of BiBaKFeO₃ showing the elemental composition in oxides

#	Thick	Type	Error	Units	Density	Norm.	Total
1	0.00	Bulk	0.00	mg/cm2	0.00F	On	100.00

Sample Layer	Table Component	Type	Concn.	Error	Units	Mole%	Error
1	SiO2	Calc	6.981	0.968	wt.%	15.682	2.176
1	V2O5	Calc	0.573	0.134	wt.%	0.425	0.099
1	Cr2O3	Calc	0.000	0.000	wt.%	0.000	0.000
1	MnO	Calc	0.073	0.034	wt.%	0.138	0.065
1	Fe2O3	Calc	21.753	0.193	wt.%	18.388	0.163
1	CoO	Calc	0.097	0.054	wt.%	0.174	0.098
1	NiO	Calc	0.000	0.000	wt.%	0.000	0.000
1	CuO	Calc	0.122	0.018	wt.%	0.206	0.031
1	Nb2O5	Calc	0.018	0.058	wt.%	0.009	0.030
1	WO3	Calc	0.037	0.068	wt.%	0.021	0.040
1	P2O5	Calc	0.000	0.000	wt.%	0.000	0.000
1	SO3	Calc	0.502	0.629	wt.%	0.846	1.060
1	CaO	Calc	0.493	0.070	wt.%	1.187	0.170
1	MgO	Calc	2.217	8.496	wt.%	7.424	28.454
1	K2O	Calc	0.337	0.079	wt.%	0.482	0.113
1	BaO	Calc	31.966	0.516	wt.%	28.142	0.454
1	Al2O3	Calc	4.167	2.076	wt.%	5.517	2.748
1	Ta2O5	Calc	0.000	0.000	wt.%	0.000	0.000
1	TiO2	Calc	2.388	0.179	wt.%	4.036	0.302
1	ZnO	Calc	0.017	0.014	wt.%	0.028	0.023
1	Ag2O	Calc	0.000	0.000	wt.%	0.000	0.000
1	Cl	Calc	2.448	0.235	wt.%	9.320	0.896
1	ZrO2	Calc	0.078	0.146	wt.%	0.085	0.160
1	SnO2	Calc	0.000	0.000	wt.%	0.000	0.000
1	PbO	Calc	0.266	0.293	wt.%	0.161	0.177
1	Rb2O	Calc	0.518	0.131	wt.%	0.374	0.094
1	Cs2O	Calc	0.365	0.529	wt.%	0.175	0.253
1	SrO	Calc	0.054	0.030	wt.%	0.070	0.039
1	Bi2O3	Calc	24.532	0.276	wt.%	7.107	0.080

Figure 1: XRD of BiKbBaFeO₃ showing the phase composition

Figure 2: FTIR of BiKbBaFeO₃ showing bond types within identified wavelength

Figure 3: TEM of BiKBaFeO₃ showing nano size crystals formed

Table 2: Amount of Hydrogen yield with Catalyst loading

S/No	Amount of Catalyst (g/l)	Hydrogen (H ₂) yield (Mmol ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ g ⁻¹)
1	0.1	65
2	0.25	113
3	0.5	204
4	0.75	245
5	1.0	216

Table 3: Amount of Hydrogen yield with Ni Co-catalyst loading

S/No	Amount of Co-catalyst (g/l)	Hydrogen (H ₂) yield (Mmol ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ g ⁻¹)
1	0.1	65
2	0.25	113
3	0.5	204
4	0.75	245
5	1.0	216

Table 4: Amount of Hydrogen yield with Methanol concentration

S/No	Concentration (%)	Hydrogen (H ₂) yield (Mmol ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ g ⁻¹)
1	0	35
2	5	140
3	10	220
4	15	290
5	20	270

Table 5: Amount of Hydrogen yield over pH

S/No	pH	Hydrogen (H ₂) yield (Mmol ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ g ⁻¹)
1	2	300
2	4	270
3	6	210
4	8	150
5	10	120

Conclusion

BiKBaFeO₃ photocatalyst was synthesized using sol-gel method, the product calcined at 850°C. The characterization results for XRF, XRD, TEM and FTIR indicated the BiKBaFeO₃ synthesized without impurities. The

high quality compared to several other potential semiconductor based photocatalysts reported of similar methodology, may be due to higher calcinations temperature to improve its physical properties. The optimum amounts of the parameters necessary for the photocatalysis of

BiK₂BaFeO₃-ethanol assisted water splitting reaction for H₂ generation indicated that beyond the presented threshold, H₂ yield was inhibited. Preparations of similar BiK₂BaFeO₃ perovskites are in progress and the comparative effect of necessary parameters to achieve further improvement in hydrogen generation.

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